

HR STRATEGIES: A PREREQUISITE FOR WRITING SUCCESS STORIES OF ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Objective-To win the battle of global competition in this turbulent environment strong HR strategies are needed by the organizations. Business strategies cannot be formulated without good HR strategies. In the environment of economic uncertainties, competing priorities, limited resources and managerial complexities organizations are working to create a value of their human resource. Organizations can put their best foot forward only after having a talented and skilled workforce and also by establishing a good relationship with them. Objective of the paper is to provide an insight to the managers for developing the most competitive HR strategies like talent management strategy and leadership development strategy with which global competition can be won. Secondary objective is to analyze and eliminate those practices which are not fruitful for the organization's success.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet. In order to have a practical experience, this paper has also analyzed successful implementation of HR strategies at various organizations.

Findings- Effective formulation of HR strategies is needed for winning the global competition. By implementing sound HR strategies organizations can face the market competition and can achieve all the heights of success.

Limitations-Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.

Practical implications-This paper can inspire managers and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in their existing HR strategies for better future. By implementing sound HR strategies organizations can become more competitive.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of organizations following different HR strategies and also includes literature review about leadership and talent management, which promotes unique and interesting contributions in HRM research.

Key words: HR strategies, talent management strategy, leadership development strategy, Gen Y

Introduction

All over the world drastic changes are occurring in the business environment. Due to globalization of business operations, unprecedented growth of information technology and cross country culture in work situations, the management of organizations have really become a big challenge. The dynamic environment forces organizations to be flexible, innovative and responsive. As a result of this Human Resources (HR) are forced to raise the bar and to act as a change agent, who formulates strategies for beating the global competition. Earlier HR role was confined with just matching the job descriptions with job specifications, cost cuttings and efficiency drives but nowadays HR

is required to handle various challenges like employee engagement, managing global and virtual workforce, conforming to cross-cultural talent needs, outsourcing low value activities and ensuring judicious use of technology not just for business but also for people. The new generation managers are more occupied with the problem of handling multi-skill knowledge workers who have more of higher order needs and a changed set of expectations towards organization. The value of human capital can be increased by creating a vibrant and lively environment in the work setting. Sophisticated technological structure of organization can be made more productive by adding social and human structures with changed norms and values to it. Organizations can achieve all this by doing a lot of homework in preparing good HR strategies and then implementing them carefully to the desired satisfaction level. Relevant steps are required to be taken by the organizations for revising their existing business strategies and planning for the new ones.

Review of literature

According to Wright and McMahan (1992) strategic HRM is “the pattern of planned human resource deployments and activities which supports organization in the achievement of its goals.”Alcazar, Fernandez and Gardy (2005) defined strategic HRM as “the integrated set of practices, policies and strategies through which organizations manage their human capital that influences and is influenced by the business strategy. Business strategies once formulated are required to be implemented by the managers who in turn can influence others for the implementation of the strategy.

According to J. P. Howell & Costley, 2006 managers are those people who can influence their subordinates in such a manner that they are ready to contribute their personal resources e.g., time, efforts, skills, knowledge, abilities to support the organizational goal.

A manager can be a leader only if he has at least one subordinate who is willing to follow him (DeRue & Ashforth, 2010).This followership increases manager’s self-confidence and sense of empowerment, thus enhancing the manager’s courage and motivation to make difficult decisions or to set bold and inspiring goals, such as those championed by charismatic leaders (J. M. Howell & Shamir, 2005; Lapierre, Bremner, & McMullan, 2012).

Employee retention is one of the major concerns of any organization in a high-growth business (Peterson, 2005). Employee retention is important because employees are the most valuable asset in any organization (Adebayo, 2001; Ejiofor and Mbachu, 2001).So adequate employee retention strategies are required to be implemented in order to achieve the goals and objectives of any organization.

Organizations are required to provide an energetic and vibrant environment where young leaders can grow. Human beings need development in multiple directions for which several managerial practices are required like enriching knowledge, enhancing skills, modifying behaviors, bringing attitudinal changes, facilitating job adjustment and career advancements. It also includes developing in the profession through coaching, mentoring and counseling and in many other facets. Coaching is mainly for professional development in the job role, mentoring is for developing leadership at work and counseling for helping people cope with adverse situations (Haldar 2008).

Saxena and Tiwari (2009) explored the HRM Practices adopted by leading IT Companies such as TATA, Infosys and Wipro in India. They implemented HRM practices like sound Training and Development, Employer-Employee Relations, Recognition through Rewards, Culture building, Career Development, Compensation and Benefits as important HRM Practices.

Leadership Development Strategy

Conglomerates are required to be strong leaders who can foster and can generate an environment of developing young leaders. Strong visionaries can create an environment of mutual trust and confidence where young leaders can be nurtured. Such organizations have a great future wherein under the umbrella of one strong leader, numerous small leaders could emerge. At the top strong leader creates all the differences because it is his vision which moves down the line. If he is having a vision of developing leaders from within the organization, leaders would definitely emerge. Such young leaders with vibrant energy can take the lead in their hands under the supervision and mentorship of their superiors and an overall environment of self stimulation can be developed. Organization with empowered employees and self managed teams shows good results and develops the ability to withstand all the odds of turbulent market environment.

In 12th HRM Summit organized by AIMA on 16th Dec 2014, Mr. D. Shivkumar, Chairman and CEO of PepsiCo India private limited emphasized that HR strategy should not be considered different from business strategy and HR strategies must be in sync with the business strategies. For the growth and success of a company HR must act as a navigator with companies. He suggested that leaders must be culturally agile, generationally savvy (how to handle various generations), must have team building ability, with broad horizon and must be an inspirational communicator to win globally. Leadership is a top priority issue for organizations.

At the summit other speakers like Sunil Kant Munjal, Joint Managing Director, Hero Moto Corp Ltd. and Naila Lal Kidwai, Chairman HSBC Pacific have thrown light on the fact that senior leaders inside their companies must develop a culture where young leaders can grow, which is ultimately beneficial to both the organization as well as the employee. Mr. Munjal discussed that nowadays younger people are more vocal and have more expectations from the organizations. They have a lot of potential for becoming good leaders but there is a fear of insecurity amongst the senior leaders that juniors can overtake their position. Such youngsters must be nurtured by the senior leaders to grow in their careers.

Great companies can never be built or sustained without great leader e.g., Reliance would not have been possible without Dhirubhai Ambani, nor Infosys without Narayan Murthy.

Infosys leadership model

On August 20, 2006, at the age of 60, N R Narayana Murthy took retirement from the position of the company's chief mentor and chairman, Infosys Technologies Ltd. He said: "I do feel sad, but am happy too. It is a mixed feeling. It's like getting your daughter married: you are sad that she is going away, but happy that there is someone younger -- and stronger -- to take care of her." He said that it is necessary to appreciate the power of youth and to create opportunities for them so that they could be nurtured.

Company had a good succession plan as a result of which we have seen a smooth transition of authority and leadership from Narayan Murthy to Nandan Nilekani to Chris Gopalakrishnan. Infosys continues to be in very good hands to take on any challenge and is the organization which has set a great example of strong leadership development. The company keeps on focusing on the development and emergence of young leaders for which it has established a leadership development institute which is inspiring the young leaders for taking the lead in their hands. Infosys had a program called "Leaders Teach" in which leaders use psychometrics to identify current leaders who could be exceptionally effective in the "Infosys leadership model". Leaders share their personal experiences about where they stumbled in the past to help juniors in avoiding the same mistakes.

During 25th anniversary celebrations of Infosys Leadership Institute Mysore campus, S 'Kris' Gopalakrishnan, Chief Operating Officer and Deputy Managing Director, Infosys told that a pool of 400 leaders is identified across the globe on the basis of their performance throughout their tenure for leadership training. There is a three-tier mentoring process at Infosys.

Tier-1 consists of the company's Board of Directors as mentors, Tier-2 leaders who in turn guide the Tier-3 group. About 45 executives are a part of the company's Tier-1 of the management council. And each of the leaders undergoes exhaustive and sustained training through the company's personal development programme -- PDP.

"Creativity, ethical and sincerity and the commitment to pursuit excellence are major considerations while identifying future leaders at Infosys," adds Gopalakrishnan.

Innovation - Reinventing Tata Steel: ASPIRE Initiative for Cost-Competitiveness

During the 1990s, the Company re-engineered its business processes, established its cost leadership in a liberalized scenario and modernized its operations to become one of the most efficient steel producers in the world. After a period of recessionary conditions in the early part of the century, the steel industry scenario changed dramatically in 2003 led by the strong growth in China. The Company was prepared to participate in this opportunity and set out on the growth and globalization path in the 21st century.

The Company realized the need to grow in size and regional diversity to match global players. In 2005, the Company made long term plans of becoming a 50 million tons steel producer by 2015 having multi-locational manufacturing facilities with strong regional presence focusing mainly on auto, packaging and construction sectors across the global markets.

Tata steel mobilized more than a hundred teams to bring about improvement in different areas. The company entrusted around 5000 people with the challenge of carrying out initiatives to 'modernize the mindsets' of 40,000 employees of the company. Improvements were found in different areas like- enhanced quality, increased performance, augmented total operation performance (TOP), created a market oriented organization, improved technology, started adding new facilities for manufacturing value added products, capacity expansion and so forth.

Tata Steel took the initiative termed as 'ASPIRE', which denoted 'Aspirational Initiatives to Retain Excellence'. Tata Steel formed teams, ignited the members and used teams as instruments and a source of innovation in the company. Tata steel trained the entire workforce in certain improvement techniques and in changing the pattern of thinking.

The intention of the Tata Steel management was to enhance the 'insights of the workforce and their capabilities, make them look at the objects and operations with 'new eyes' be innovative, think and transform the thoughts into actions, dream and translate dreams into reality, finally doing work efficiently. Tata Steel is rated among the top five steel producers in the world by world steel dynamics. Tata Steel became the lowest cost steel producer in the world and was ranked the best company in the world in 2005.

Talent Management Strategies for future success

Nowadays almost every company have started working on talent management and they realized that they are required to be very practical while dealing with an employee with right skills, knowledge, abilities and behaviors to achieve strategic business objectives (Morgan and Jardin, 2010). Talent management has taken the attention of every

one including researchers, practitioners, consultants, organizations and academicians. Everyone has explained talent management in their own terms so it is very necessary to understand talent management for facing the global competition. After 1998, McKinsey created the phrase “War of Talent”, which addressed the issue of growing shortage of talent. This “War of Talent”, encouraged the companies to focus on the issue of talent management for winning global wars (Beechler and Woodward, 2009). Different companies are adopting different strategies in a unique manner for implementing talent management.

Talent management strategy includes various activities like performance management, career management, succession management, leadership development, skill development and talent acquisition.

Talent management is the cycle which starts at manpower planning for an organization, thereafter recruiting the employees and then *managing the entire lifecycle of employee till he leaves organization*. Talent management is gaining strategic importance in this phase of growth in global organizations. To face the global competition companies have no choice other than talent acquisition and capability development.

As a result of tools like LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook talent mobility has increased nowadays, as a result of which people can find new jobs easily with the help of these networking sites. It is a big threat to the employers because talent from within the organization would move in search of growth and career to other organizations. So employers are needed to provide internal talent mobility and career growth in their own organizations. Nowadays "Facilitated talent mobility" strategy is required which includes open access to internal positions, employee assessment tools and leadership values focusing on internal development. In the absence of talent management practices employees would no longer look for a career within the organization rather they would be working just for gaining experience. Thus facilitated talent mobility strategy suggests that identify talent from within the organizations, then engage, motivate and retain them for better results.

For talent management, Human Resource is required to be integrated with Organization Development. Jardin, 2010 defined integrated talent management which is a combination of both HR and OD. Jardin 2010, explained domain of HR work is to acquire, deploy, develop and retain talent. Domain of OD work is concerned with wisely planning to get high level of performance and engagement in the organization.

Gen Y will Transform the Workplace

A successful talent strategy depends on an organization’s understanding of what pushes and motivates its employees across all generations. Organizations today are busy in understanding the aspirations and needs of Gen Y and accordingly changing their policies to have good results from them. For making Gen Y more efficient some policies of the organizations are needed to be changed, only then organizations can win the competition.

Vishal Shah, VP Wipro Ltd. is of the opinion that Gen Y expects a lot from the companies, they are creative, do not like long hours, want flexibility, are tech savvy and they draw energy from their friends. He also added one important thing that we cannot expect loyalty from Gen Y as soon as they get good opportunities they prefer leaving the job. But whatever the duration company is able to retain them, they can add a lot of value to the company in that time period.

Leaders are required to bring positive changes to the working culture of the organization as they are free to add on some new things like social media to the existing traditional system of doing work. This would definitely result in a more engaged and high-performing workforce and delivering true innovation to customers. An immediate access to information and use of mobile technology has made today’s workers more smart and updated. So companies are

required to make the best use of new technologies, social networking sites etc. to their advantage. Many organizations have started adopting flexible working style as Gen Y is more comfortable with flexi working system. With the help of technology and social connections a huge amount of knowledge can be captured and teamwork can be established which can become fruitful for the organizations. Gen X people are also required to keep themselves open for learning from Gen Y. All this would create a learning environment and a strong team work culture within the organization.

iOpener institute for People & Performance is an international consultancy that helps organizations to achieve their strategic and commercial goals. It conducted a survey in October 2012 and gathered data regarding “how employers can retain their Gen Y talent” from 18,000 global professionals. Findings were that pay and financial rewards are important to Gen Y, they do not want to be underpaid for their work but there was *no significant correlation between increased levels of pay and greater talent retention*. Instead research suggested a *strong correlation between job satisfaction and talent retention*. Gen Y is not ready to continue with the jobs which make them unhappy.

A correlation was noted between the trust that Gen Y employees have in their leaders' vision, and their intention to leave the organization. In other words if Gen Y is convinced with the strategies made by their boss then they will also contribute positively in the achievement of those strategies.

According to a 2012 report by the Kauffman Foundation (the largest entrepreneurial foundation in the US), 29.4 % of entrepreneurs were found between the age of 20 to 34 years. Recruitment of the right talent for this young generation pool of entrepreneurs is again a tough task which raised a global war of searching the right talent and skills in sectors such as technology.

In an HRM summit organized by AIMA, 16th Dec 2014, Yuvraj Srivastava, VP Make My Trip Ltd. discussed that “we cannot expect loyalty from Gen Y as soon as they get good opportunities they prefer leaving the job. But whatever the duration company is able to retain them, they can add a lot of value to the company in that time period”.

No organization wanted to invest on the employees who are going to leave the organization in few days. Nowadays there is a problem of job mobility with the Gen Y so organizations are suggested to develop certain strategies of job fulfillment and enjoyable working environment with which it can bind Gen Y. In order to retain employees a career plan must be shown to them so that they can understand the opportunities within the company and can see a path of progression and job fulfillment. Companies must also ensure that there is transparency in the system along with recognition of work.

According to the third edition of **Fortune India's Most Admired Companies (IMAC) research** it was found that ITC is the most admired Indian company for the year 2014. Fortune India, in association with global management consultancy, Hay Group, prepared an annual report card on corporate reputation and found that ITC scored the highest on parameters such as corporate governance, endurance, social impact, product's quality and employee empowerment. L&T ranked second and has scored highest on leadership while HUL scored the third position and scored highest on investment, talent development, product quality, leadership, innovativeness and global footprint.

Top ten Fortune India's Most Admired Companies

1. ITC
2. L&T
3. Hindustan Unilever
4. Maruti Suzuki
5. State Bank of India
6. TCS
7. Coca Cola India
8. Samsung India Electronics
9. Tata Motors
10. ONGC

Survey was based on the methodology of peer ranking in which respondents were supposed to rank their peers on a scale of ten parameters. Parameters included were corporate governance, endurance, impact on society, investment value, product/service quality, innovation, quality of leadership, talent development, employee empowerment and business footprint. In this unique peer ranking survey 523 companies across the economy's 15 key sectors were covered and had 443 respondents. In the first phase of the research top three companies from each sector were found which in total gave top 45 companies. In phase two these 45 companies were shortlisted to top ten on the same parameters. Sridhar Ganesan, Country Head, Hay Group India, comments, "This year, two criteria in particular, corporate governance and social impact, separated the Top 10 from the rest of the winners. ITC has topped the list by displacing group company TCS in 2014."

In order to have a good rank companies are required to work on the above mentioned parameters and are required to be aggressive while bringing changes in their current strategies.

Conclusion

Leaders with strong vision are required to meet the global challenges. Influencing leaders who can visualize the future problems and can take some steps in the form of revised strategies and revised HR policies are going to create a mark in the history, whose footsteps are surely going to be followed by the young and emerging leaders. Nowadays economy is reviving and multinational companies are booming, creating an atmosphere of strict global competition, this is surely arising a question of talent management, employee retention and a need to be more creative and innovative than before. Revised HR strategies are required which can meet the needs of Gen Y and can address various higher order needs of their people. Companies like Infosys, TCS, Tata Steel, ITC, HUL etc. are following the best HR strategies for facing the global competition. A satisfied employee is happy and more productive. No matter how talented an employee is, that talent or potential will remain untapped unless and until he is not satisfied and happy with his organization. Most of the time organizations are represented by the managers or the leaders, so leaders are required to possess leadership skills with which they can manage the show and can encourage more young leaders to grow under his shadow.

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